

Enhancing Collective Bargaining between Employers and Employees in Zimbabwe's Informal Sector

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Abstract:

This article examines the right to collective bargaining for informal sector employees in Zimbabwe. It argues that the current academic discourse in Zimbabwe has perceived informal sector employees as a homogeneous unit confronting identical challenges. Thus, the article departs from a point that recognises the existence of employment relationships in many businesses that fall under the informal economy. Importantly, it shows that there are employers and wage earners who fit within the definitions of 'employer' and 'employee' as provided by labour legislation. It achieves this end by adopting a qualitative analysis of the existing body of knowledge on informal employees and manages to identify its gaps. It is demonstrated that the primary sources of the right of employees to collective bargaining in Zimbabwe are the Constitution of Zimbabwe and the Labour Act. The right to collective bargaining that is enshrined in these sources fully applies to informal sector employees. However, these employees face many organisational challenges that make it impossible for them to fully enjoy their right to collective bargaining. Some of these challenges include the absence of formal employment contracts in the informal sector, lack of knowledge of informal players' rights and obligations, resource constraints that enable them to formally organise, and lack of commitment to organise and enforce collective bargaining rights. In that regard, solutions are suggested that can assist in making sure that the marginalised informal sector employees are able to fully enjoy their right to collective bargaining in Zimbabwe. These include a stronger push towards formalisation of the economy through the right policies by the government, the creation of bargaining councils through the intervention of the State, enhanced labour inspections to ensure compliance with labour laws, awareness campaigns and promoting unity among the informal sector employees.

Keywords: Employer, Employee, Labour Act, Collective Bargaining, Informal Sector, Zimbabwe.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This article examines strategies to enhance collective bargaining between employers and employees within the informal sector. An important issue in Zimbabwe is that the current literature fails to distinguish between employers and employees in this sector as separate entities. Consequently, both groups are perceived as a homogeneous unit confronting identical challenges. Thus, the article departs from a point that recognises the existence of employment relationships in many businesses that fall under the informal economy. By definition, informal economy refers to all lawful economic activities by employees and economic units that are not covered or insufficiently covered by formal arrangements in both law and practice.¹ On the other hand, collective bargaining involves a process of negotiations between employers and employees or their representative organisations with a view to agreeing on terms and conditions of employment.²

This right to collective bargaining is recognised by the Constitution of Zimbabwe³ and the Labour Act.⁴ Thus, the labour law in Zimbabwe contemplates the existence of employment relationships in both the formal and informal sector. Despite the recognition of employees in the informal sector by the law with the attendant rights which include the right to collective bargaining, these basic rights are virtually unavailable to this category of employees in practice. This is against the background that the informal economy accounts for 88% of the total employment in Zimbabwe although the majority of these employees are self-employed.⁵ However, not all employees in the informal sector are self-employed as some employees are employed by others in employer-employee relationships. Thus, this article discusses the legal framework on collective bargaining in Zimbabwe. This is done in order to show the scope and import of the right to collective bargaining in Zimbabwe which includes employees in the informal sector. It then proceeds to discuss the challenges that face these employees' organisational capacity. Finally, solutions that can result in the greater participation of these employees in activities that ensure that they enjoy the benefits of collective bargaining are proffered.

2. THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK IN ZIMBABWE

The legal framework on collective bargaining that applies to employees in the informal sector is mainly derived from the Constitution of Zimbabwe and the Labour Act. These are, in turn, discussed separately below in order to evaluate the application of their provisions to the employees who work in the informal sector.

¹ 'Transition from the Informal to the Formal Economy Recommendation, 2015 (No. 204)' (International Labour Organisation, 2015) at https://normlex.ilo.org/dyn/nrmlx_en/f?p=NORMLEXPUB:12100:0::NO::P12100_ILO_CODE:R204 (last visited 23 December 2024).

² Lovemore Madhuku, *Labour Law in Zimbabwe* (Harare: Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, 2015) 319.

³ Constitution of Zimbabwe Amendment (No. 20) Act, 2013 (Constitution of Zimbabwe).

⁴ Labour Act [Chapter 28:01] (Labour Act).

⁵ Munyaradzi Gwisai and Edzai Edson Matika (eds), *Paralegal Handbook for The Informal Economy in Zimbabwe* (Harare: ZCIEA, ZCTU, ILAW, 2024) 3.

2.1 The Constitution of Zimbabwe

The Constitution of Zimbabwe introduced labour rights as part of its declaration of rights for the first time in Zimbabwe in 2013. For the purposes of this discussion, it provides for an overarching right of every person to fair labour practices and standards which include the right to be paid a fair and reasonable wage.⁶ To that end, the Constitution of Zimbabwe rests on the principle of 'fairness' which should guide the application of labour practices and standards in Zimbabwe. This also entails that employees in the informal sector should equally enjoy the right to collective bargaining just like their counterparts in the formal sector. Further, the Constitution of Zimbabwe stipulates that all employees, employers, trade unions, and organisations representing employees or employers possess the right to engage in collective bargaining.⁷ However, members of the security services are excluded from enjoying this right. The meaning of the words, 'employer', 'employee', 'trade union' and 'employers' organisation' are defined in the Labour Act which gives effect to the constitutional provisions on collective bargaining.

The Labour Act defines an 'employer' as any person who hires or offers employment to another person and compensates or explicitly or implicitly agrees to compensate that person and it includes the manager, agent or representative of such person who is in charge or control of the work upon which such other person is employed.⁸ The employer also includes a judicial manager, a liquidator, a trustee or an executor of a deceased estate. When applied to the informal sector, it means any person who is operating an informal business and is capable of employing another person who becomes an employee. In that regard, the Labour Act defines an employee as:⁹

Any person who performs work or services for another person for remuneration or reward on such terms and conditions as agreed upon by the parties or as provided for in this Act, and includes a person performing work or services for another person- (a) in circumstances where, even if the person performing the work or services supplies his own tools or works under flexible conditions of service, the hirer provides substantial investment in or assumes the substantial risk of the undertaking; or (b) in any other circumstances that more closely resemble the relationship between an

⁶ Section 65 (1) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

⁷ *ibid.*, section 65(5). It also provides for other rights such as the right to organise, and to form and join federations of trade unions or other organisations.

⁸ Section 2 of the Labour Act.

⁹ *ibid.*

employee and employer than that between an independent contractor and hirer of services.

Thus, the Labour Act evidently offers an extensive definition of the term 'employee,' to encompass scenarios that closely mirror the relationship between an employer and an employee. The advantages of this wider definition is that it applies to many employment relationships in the informal sector. This is because the informal sector is characterised by numerous relationships which may not be easily categorised as an employment one. However, the exclusion of independent contractors from the definition of 'employee' under the Labour Act implies that they are not entitled to the constitutional right to engage in collective bargaining.¹⁰

A trade union is defined as any association or organisation established to advocate for or promote the interests of employees or a specific group of employees concerning their employment.¹¹ In that regard, the Constitution of Zimbabwe recognises the right of every person to form and join trade unions of their choice and to participate in the lawful activities of that trade union.¹² It follows that the words 'every person' includes all persons who are entitled to enjoy the aforementioned rights, including those in the informal sector. On the other hand, an employer's organisation means any association or organisation established to advocate for or promote the interests of employers or their groups concerning employment-related issues.¹³ Just like employees in the informal sector, employers have a constitutional right to form, join and participate in the activities of employers' organisations of their choice.¹⁴

The constitutional recognition of the right of employees to collective bargaining in order to improve their conditions of work in its declaration of rights has far-reaching implications. For instance, courts and other relevant bodies are mandated to fully uphold the rights and freedoms established in the declaration of rights which include informal sector employees' right to collective bargaining in their interpretative functions.¹⁵ In that regard, courts are constitutionally obligated to adopt a broader interpretation in order to fully uphold employees' right to collective bargaining, rather than opting for a more limited interpretation.¹⁶ It is also imperative for courts and other relevant bodies to consider international law, as well as treaties and conventions to which Zimbabwe is a signatory, when interpreting the declaration of rights.¹⁷ The consequence of this approach is that courts ought to refer to international law ratified

¹⁰ James Tsabora and Tapiwa G. Kasuso, 'Reflections on the Constitutionalising of Individual Labour law and Labour Rights in Zimbabwe' (2017) 38 *Industrial Law Journal* 54.

¹¹ Section 2 of the Labour Act.

¹² Section 65(2) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

¹³ Section 2 of the Labour Act.

¹⁴ n 12 above.

¹⁵ Section 46(1)(a) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

¹⁶ Alfred Mavedzenge and Doug J. Coltart, *A Constitutional Law Guide Towards Understanding Zimbabwe's Fundamental Socio-economic and Cultural Human Rights* (Harare: Zimbabwe Human Rights Association, 2014) 20.

¹⁷ Section 46(1) (c) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

by Zimbabwe, which has predominantly addressed the overarching right of employees to freedom of association, as well as provisions that specifically focus on employees within the informal sector.¹⁸

Further, the inclusion of the right of employees to collective bargaining in the declaration of rights also means that the State as well as natural and juristic persons are bound by its provisions.¹⁹ This fortifies the vertical and horizontal application of the declaration of rights. To that end, the State and informal sector employers have a duty to protect the informal sector employees' right to collective bargaining.²⁰ The declaration of rights can be applied either directly or indirectly. In cases of indirect application, the objective is to determine if the standard legal principles or customary laws, encompassing legislation, common law, or customary practices, are in alignment with it.²¹ Conversely, when applied directly, the declaration of rights creates a distinct array of specific remedies, including declaratory orders, interdicts and damages.²² Thus, the employees in the informal sector can enforce their rights to collective bargaining through the Labour Act which gives effect to their constitutional right or they can raise a violation of the provisions of the declaration of rights which becomes a constitutional matter.

2.2 The Labour Act

As alluded to earlier on, the Labour Act is the principal piece of legislation that has detailed provisions on the informal sector employees' right to collective bargaining. To start with, the Labour Act does not provide a definition for the term 'collective bargaining', however, it does define a collective bargaining agreement as an agreement that is "negotiated" under its provisions, which governs the "terms and conditions of employment for employees."²³ Hence, the Labour Act envisions collective bargaining as a process of negotiation.²⁴ In the case of *TM Supermarket v TM National Workers' Committee*²⁵ the court determined that negotiation refers to a dialogue between the

¹⁸ Examples include Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise Convention, 1948 (No. 87); Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention, 1949 (No. 98); Transition from the Informal to the Formal Economy Recommendation, 2015 (No. 204); African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights; Charter of Fundamental Social Rights in SADC.

¹⁹ Section 45 of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

²⁰ *ibid*, section 44.

²¹ Howard Chitimira, 'Selected Challenges and Prospects of the Zimbabwe Constitution of 2013 in Protection of Human Rights and Constitutional Democracy in Zimbabwe' (2017) *Stell LR* 359.

²² De Vos and others, *South African Constitutional Law in Context* (Cape Town: Oxford University Press, 2014) 323.

²³ Section 2 of the Labour Act.

²⁴ Madhuku, n 2 above, 319. In the case of *Metal & Allied Workers' Union v Hart Ltd* (1985) 6 ILJ 478 (IC), the South African Industrial Court, which is now known as the Labour Court, determined that bargaining is distinct from simple consultations. The court clarified that consultation entails merely the gathering of information or advice without resulting in any form of agreement, while bargaining involves a reciprocal exchange aimed at reaching a consensus. Additionally, the court noted that the term 'negotiate' is synonymous with bargaining.

²⁵ SC-19-04.

involved parties aimed at reaching a resolution on a specific matter. Nevertheless, it acknowledged that disagreements may still arise following negotiations, which does not imply that the negotiation process was absent.

The Labour Act provides for the existence of two tiers of collective bargaining, that is, one at the workplace level and another at the industry level.²⁶ Collective bargaining at the workplace level occurs between the employer and the workers' committee representing the employees.²⁷ Collective bargaining at the workplace level occurs under three specific circumstances. Firstly, in the absence of a suitable trade union representing the employees, the workers' committee serves as the sole legal representative for those employees at the workplace.²⁸ Secondly, if there exists an appropriate trade union for the employees but it does not have a collective bargaining agreement with the employer in question, workplace collective bargaining can take place on condition that there is written authorisation from the relevant trade union.²⁹ Thirdly, when a collective bargaining agreement is established for a particular industry, workplace collective bargaining is limited to the extent allowed by that industry-wide agreement.³⁰ To that end, a workplace collective bargaining agreement becomes binding only when it receives the endorsement of the appropriate trade union and is approved by over fifty percent of the employees at that workplace.³¹ It is evident from the circumstances surrounding collective bargaining at the workplace level that trade unions are afforded a more significant role in the process of workplace collective bargaining. Hence, they can play a crucial role in improving the working conditions of employees in the informal sector.

On the other hand, collective bargaining at the industry level occurs between registered trade unions and employers or their organisations, which may include federations.³² It is conducted through employment councils.³³ The Labour Act provides for two categories of collective bargaining agreements that may be negotiated at the industry level, that is, statutory collective bargaining agreements and non-statutory collective bargaining agreements.³⁴ Statutory collective bargaining agreements are established through negotiations involving registered trade unions and employers or their respective organisations and federations. In contrast, non-statutory collective bargaining agreements arise from discussions between unregistered trade unions and unregistered employers' organisations. Statutory collective bargaining must adhere to

²⁶ Madhuku, n 2 above, 327.

²⁷ Section 24 of the Labour Act.

²⁸ *ibid*, section 24 (2).

²⁹ *ibid*, section 24 (3) (a).

³⁰ *ibid*, section 24 (3) (c).

³¹ *Ibid*, section 25(1).

³² *ibid*, section 74.

³³ *ibid*, Part viii.

³⁴ *ibid*, section 74.

the stipulations outlined in the Labour Act, whereas non-statutory collective bargaining is regulated by common law principles.³⁵

The recognition of non-statutory collective agreements allows informal sector employees to negotiate binding collective bargaining agreements with their employers outside the Labour Act. However, it has been observed that the lack of legislative measures that mandate good faith negotiations and deter unfair labour practices in non-statutory collective bargaining constitutes a gap in Zimbabwean law.³⁶ This is because the absence of protections such as the requirement to negotiate in good faith in non-statutory collective bargaining becomes more evident in negotiations in the informal sector where most employers and employees do not belong to registered organisations or trade unions respectively.

In statutory collective bargaining agreements, it constitutes an unfair labour practice for an employer to refuse to engage in good faith negotiations with a workers' committee or a trade union that has been properly established to represent employees in these discussions.³⁷ The obligation to engage in good faith negotiations is significantly enhanced by section 75 of the Labour Act. This section mandates that parties must reveal all pertinent information related to the negotiations, refrain from making false or misleading representations concerning the subjects of bargaining, and strive to achieve a timely and successful resolution of disputes. Moreover, section 75 of the Labour Act elevates the standard of good faith by stipulating that parties must negotiate in "absolute good faith." Additionally, if a party claims financial incapacity as a justification for not accepting any terms during negotiations, it is required to fully disclose its financial status to the other party.

Trade unions and employers in Zimbabwe have a greater latitude to engage in negotiations for collective bargaining agreements concerning any employment conditions that are of shared interest to both parties involved.³⁸ The Labour Act then presents a non-exhaustive enumeration of topics that may be included in the agenda for collective bargaining, including deductions from wages, occupational safety requirements, working hours, and overtime, among other matters.³⁹ In the matter of *Catering Employees Association of Zimbabwe v Zimbabwe Hotel and Catering Workers*

³⁵ Munyaradzi Gwisai, *Labour & Employment Law in Zimbabwe: Relations of Work Under Neo-colonial Capitalism* (Harare: Zimbabwe Labour Centre and Institute of Commercial Law, 2006) 316.

³⁶ Caleb H. Mucheche, *A Guide to Collective Bargaining Law & Wage Negotiations in Zimbabwe* (Harare: African Dominion Publications, 2014) 37.

³⁷ Section 8 (c) of the Labour Act.

³⁸ *ibid*, section 74 (2).

³⁹ *ibid*, section 74 (2).

*Union & Anor*⁴⁰, the Court affirmed the necessity of adopting a wide interpretation of the term “any conditions of employment which are of mutual interest to the parties.” It was determined that this phrase encompasses any issue that may be relevant to the parties involved. Thus, there is greater scope for employers and employees in the informal sector to negotiate anything that is relevant to their employment relationship which could also mean requesting an employer to ensure safe and health conditions at the workplace through negotiating with third parties. This is because informal sector employees are usually exposed to many health hazards including absence of shelter and ablution facilities at their workplaces.

For an industry level collective bargaining agreement to become binding, it is required to be submitted to the Registrar for the purpose of registration.⁴¹ The responsible Minister has a discretion to direct the Registrar not to register a collective bargaining agreement if it appears to him or her that it is inconsistent with any legal provision or is contrary to public policy provided the issue of public interest at stake is given in writing.⁴² The stipulation mandating the Minister to clarify the nature of the public interest at hand is a recent amendment incorporated into the Labour Act in 2023.⁴³ Previously, the Minister was not required to explain the nature of the public interest before making a decision to refuse the registration of a collective bargaining agreement. This was oppressive and contrary to the rules of natural justice that require decisions to be backed by reasons. In instances where a collective bargaining agreement has not been registered or approved until it has been modified, it is the responsibility of the involved parties to engage in negotiations for such amendments in absolute good faith. They are also required to actively participate in the necessary proceedings related to this process. The failure to fulfil these obligations is deemed to be an unfair labour practice.⁴⁴ Hence, the duty of utmost good faith that characterise the negotiation of statutory collective bargaining agreements is a continuous one. This has a positive effect on the outcome of such negotiations and it makes collective bargaining an effective tool for the protection of the rights and interests of employees in the informal sector.

Moreover, the Labour Act stipulates that a collective bargaining agreement is binding not only on the parties involved and their members but also on all employers, contractors, and their employees within the relevant industry or undertaking.⁴⁵ It is clearly provided that in order to ensure fair, equitable, and satisfactory working

⁴⁰ HH-206-00.

⁴¹ Section 79 of the Labour Act.

⁴² *ibid.*

⁴³ See section 27 of the Labour Amendment Act 11 of 2023.

⁴⁴ *ibid.*, section 79 (3).

⁴⁵ Section 82 of the Labour Act.

conditions in accordance with section 65(4) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe, it is essential for the public interest that the conditions to be set through collective bargaining should be uniformly established through a legally mandated system of free collective bargaining.⁴⁶ It follows that the Labour Act sets out the minimum standards for collective bargaining which must be equally applied to both the formal and informal sectors in Zimbabwe. This is done because it is in the public interest to do so. What is left is to ensure that the intentions of the legislature are realised in practice. In addition, every employer, employee, employers' organisation, trade union, or federation thereof has the right to participate in collective bargaining, as they are afforded the opportunity, either directly or indirectly under section 56 of the Labour Act, to secure representation within an employment council.⁴⁷

In that regard, the Labour Act further fortifies the constitutional right of employees to collective bargaining including those in the informal sector. Because of the existence of this broader right to collective bargaining, section 82 of the Labour Act provides that it should not be a lawful excuse for those who did not avail themselves of the opportunity to participate in collective bargaining to fail to abide by or claim not to be bound by a collective bargaining agreement freely negotiated for their industry. Thus, employees in the informal sector can clearly benefit from the collective bargaining process that is conducted by employers and employees in the formal sector if they fall in the same industry. Further, they have all the rights to participate in the collective bargaining process itself.

3. CATEGORIES OF INFORMAL EMPLOYEES

Informal employees fall into various categories and it then becomes necessary to discuss these categories. However, it should be emphasised from the onset that the general approach of the existing literature has been to treat everyone who participates in the informal economy activities as employees. This has the negative effect of blurring the existence of employer-employee relationships within that sector. The informal workforce includes individuals who are self-employed in unregistered or unincorporated enterprises, as well as wage earners engaged in informal employment, who lack social protection associated with their work.⁴⁸ There are many activities that are associated with the informal economy in Zimbabwe. Some of these activities include cross-border traders, vegetable market vendors, cottage industry and flea

⁴⁶ *ibid*, section 82 (a1)(a). This provision was recently introduced into the Labour Act through the Labour Amendment Act 11 of 2023.

⁴⁷ *ibid*, section 82 (a1) (b).

⁴⁸ Martha Chen, Chris Bonner and Françoise Carré, 'Organizing Informal Workers: Benefits, Challenges and Successes' (2015) *UNDP Human Development Report Office* 3.

market operators mainly for textiles and footwear, among others.⁴⁹ It is those who are employed by others who should enjoy the rights to collective bargaining that are bestowed by the law that has been discussed above.

Other employees who fall under informal employees are domestic employees. Despite the protections they receive in both international law⁵⁰ and domestic law⁵¹, they do not enjoy their full rights that are provided by the law including the right to collective bargaining in real practice. The organisational challenges which they face will be considered later in this article when challenges that face informal employees generally are discussed. This explains why minimum wages for domestic employees are set by the government in Zimbabwe.⁵² The problem with the minimum wages which are set by the government is that they are not a product of collective bargaining and the rates are usually very low. It means domestic employees should still organise themselves and negotiate for better working conditions with their employers. Nevertheless, minimum wages represent a crucial intervention against outright oppression of domestic employees in Zimbabwe.

However, there are some categories of activities in the informal sector in which it is difficult to identify the employer-employee relationship. An example is a contributing family employee who is by definition informally employed, regardless of whether his or her work is in formal or informal sector enterprises.⁵³ Thus, it is difficult to identify who the employer is in situations where employees are working as a family. It is submitted that under such arrangements, such relationships should not be governed by the employment contract to the extent that they do not violate important legal provisions such as the prohibition against child labour.⁵⁴

Some informal employees may be disguised as independent contractors. It has been warned that in certain regions globally, employers are increasingly utilising the designation of "independent contractor" to circumvent the establishment of an employment relationship along with its associated responsibilities, a trend that has been identified as "employer distancing."⁵⁵ This conclusion cannot be considered farfetched

⁴⁹ Rangarirai Machedze, 'Informal Economy in Zimbabwe: A Contextual Analysis' in Rangarirai Machedze (ed), *Informal Economy and Social Vulnerability in Zimbabwe* (Harare: Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, 2018) 5.

⁵⁰ See, for instance, the Domestic Workers Convention, 2011 (No. 189).

⁵¹ They fit within the definition of 'employee' in the Labour Act and are entitled to all the protections that are accorded to employees by the law.

⁵² See, for instance, Labour (Domestic Workers) Employment (Amendment) Regulations, 2022 (No. 21), SI 102 of 2022.

⁵³ Verena Schmidt and others, *Negotiations by Workers in the Informal Economy* (Geneva: ILO, 2023) 7.

⁵⁴ See section 81 of the Constitution of Zimbabwe and section 11 of the Labour Act.

⁵⁵ Susan J. Schurman and Adrienne E. Eaton (eds), (2012) *Trade Union Organizing in the Informal Economy: A Review of the Literature on Organizing in Africa, Asia, Latin America, North America and Western, Central and Eastern Europe*. (Newark: Rutgers, 2012) 9.

when applied to Zimbabwe. The Labour Act clearly excludes an independent contractor from the definition of ‘employee’ as discussed earlier on.⁵⁶ Employers can take advantage of this provision to evade from their obligations that are prescribed by labour law. Under those circumstances, regard should be had to the guidance that has been developed by courts which has resulted in five tests being developed which include the control test, the integration test, the economic reality test, the mutuality of obligation test and the multiple or dominant impression test.⁵⁷ The net effect of these tests is to ensure that employers cannot hide from their obligations to provide the basic employment standards at the workplace as many relationships are considered employment ones.

4. FORMS OF ORGANISATION BY INFORMAL EMPLOYEES

Informal employees have the ability to form various organisational structures to advocate for their rights and interests. By coming together in groups that allow them to present a unified front, they can effectively negotiate for improved working conditions in their respective workplaces. To start with, employees in the informal sector can simply exercise their right to form or join a trade union or workers’ committee of their choice as provided for by the law.⁵⁸ The constitutional right to form or join trade unions does not compel employees to register such trade unions. However, some protections of the Labour Act only apply to registered trade unions. For instance, employment councils can only be constituted by registered trade unions or their federation on one hand and employers, registered employer’s organisations or their federation on the other hand.⁵⁹ These are the ones which can only negotiate statutory collective bargaining agreements with all the attendant safeguards that have been discussed earlier on.⁶⁰ It is submitted that employees in the informal sector may benefit from the established trade unions and implement the collective bargaining agreements that these unions negotiate. This is because a collective bargaining agreement reached by a trade union at the industry level is binding on the entire industry to which it pertains.⁶¹

Another popular way of organising in the informal economy is through the formation of associations.⁶² An association can be registered as a private voluntary organisation if its objects includes “the provision of assistance in, or promotion of,

⁵⁶ n 8 above.

⁵⁷ For a detailed discussion of these tests, see Madhuku, n 2 above, 25-29.

⁵⁸ See section 65(2) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe and section 4 of the Labour Act.

⁵⁹ Section 56 of the Labour Act.

⁶⁰ See again the discussion on the provisions of the Labour Act on collective bargaining agreements.

⁶¹ n 45 above.

⁶² Chen, Bonner and Carré, n 48 above, 10.

activities aimed at uplifting the standard of living of persons or families”, among others.⁶³ Hence, an association whose objectives is to uplift the standard of living of informal employees qualifies to be registered under the Private Voluntary Organization Act. In the case of an unincorporated association, it can still acquire legal personality under Zimbabwean law if it qualifies to be a common law *universitas*. It becomes a common law *universitas* if, among other things, it has the capacity to acquire certain rights apart from the rights of the individuals forming it such as the right to own property, and perpetual succession.⁶⁴ In addition, the common law *universitas* must have a constitution. In that regard, its qualities were summarised in the case of *CT Bolts (Pvt) Ltd v Workers Committee*⁶⁵ as follows:

Under the common law, an unincorporated association, not being a legal *persona*, cannot as a general rule, sue or be sued in its name apart from the individual members, whose names have to be cited in the summons. A *universitas* on the other hand has the capacity, apart from the rights of the individuals forming it, to acquire rights and incur obligations. The position is also established that a body that has no constitution is not a *universitas* for it is the constitution that determines whether an association is or is not a *universitas*.

Thus, an association of informal employees in Zimbabwe can either be registered or unregistered provided it meets the requirements of the law for its recognition. The formation of an association has legal significance in Zimbabwe. The constitutional right to collective bargaining in Zimbabwe is available to “every employee, employer, trade union, and employee or employer’s organisation”⁶⁶ The law acknowledges the potential existence of employee organisations beyond traditional trade unions. However, such organisations are not recognised by the Labour Act for the purposes of collective bargaining. It is argued that the Labour Act should be aligned with the Constitution of Zimbabwe to recognise collective bargaining between an employer and an association representing employees.

⁶³ Section 6 as read with section 2 of the Private Voluntary Organizations Act [17:05] (Private Voluntary Organization Act).

⁶⁴ *Privatisation Agency of Zimbabwe and Another v Ukubambana Kubatana Investments (Private) Limited* SC 9/03.

⁶⁵ SC 16/12.

⁶⁶ Section 65 (5) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

It is also common to find associations that are neither registered nor common law *universitas*. They can be formed to merely act as vehicles for collective decision-making by the relevant informal sector employees. Such associations are not distinct from their members who are individually liable for their actions. Members can only sue or be sued in the name of the association to the extent that the rules of court allow them without necessarily permitting the associates to hide behind the name of that unincorporated association.⁶⁷ In some instances, it is just a matter of getting the necessary political backing.⁶⁸

There are examples of associations in Zimbabwe which include Zimbabwe Chamber of Informal Economy Associations (ZCIEA) which was formed in 2002 after 22 Informal Business Associations came together to form an apex body.⁶⁹ The ZCIEA was a brainchild of the Zimbabwe Congress of Trade Unions' (ZCTU) Informal Economy Project in 2002 which had the support of the Commonwealth Trade Union Congress (CTUC). The primary aim of this project was to formulate strategies that would link the formal and informal economies, as well as to implement educational programmes designed to integrate informal economic activities into the mainstream economy.⁷⁰ The involvement of the ZCTU in the formation of the ZCIEA is an indication that trade unions can play a crucial role in organising informal sector employees. To date, the ZCIEA has initiated a number of programmes that include membership training and empowerment, strategic partnerships, policy advocacy, assisting members with court cases and research, among many activities.⁷¹ The problem with the ZCIEA and similar organisations lies in their treatment of all individuals within the informal sector as if they are homogeneous, failing to differentiate between employers and employees. As a result, they adopt a perspective that assumes all members of this group face identical challenges. This approach overlooks the reality that employees primarily seek fair wages and a safe, healthy working environment. However, it is important to acknowledge that some of their initiatives do have a direct impact on employees within the sector. For example, when the ZCIEA engages in negotiations with local authorities for designated vending locations, it is advocating not

⁶⁷ *BDO Zimbabwe Chartered Accountants v Vela; The Auditor General of Zimbabwe v Vela* SC 61/22.

⁶⁸ For instance, an association by the name Vendors for ED was formed just before the 2023 harmonised national elections in Zimbabwe. It was an affiliate of the ruling ZANU (PF) party and campaigned for the party. Any benefits which accrued to the association's members were more of showing gratitude for that support.

⁶⁹ Nyasha Muchichwa, 'Labour's Approach to Formalising the Informal Economy in Zimbabwe' in Otoo and others (eds), *Formalising the Informal Economy: A Labour Perspective* (Harare: The African Labour Research Network, 2015) 147.

⁷⁰ Gwisai and Matika, n 5 above, 11.

⁷¹ *ibid*, 10-17.

only for the interests of employers but also for those of employees who need dignified workplaces.

In some instances, employees' organisations in the informal sector are established by pro-labour Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs). One such organisation is Women in Informal Employment: Globalizing and Organizing (WIEGO). It is a global network that supports employees in informal employment, especially women and those living in poverty through advocating for equal economic opportunities, rights and protections.⁷² It provides technical expertise on law, organising and representation, social protection, statistics, and urban policies.⁷³ To that end, it has previously released briefs that provide insights into the organisational strategies and practices within Zimbabwe's informal economy.⁷⁴ They achieve this objective through research on how informal sector employees can strengthen their position when it comes to organising into associations and engage in collective bargaining. The effectiveness of NGOs' efforts can be maximised only if they acknowledge the various groups that make up the informal sector, including the presence of employment relationships.

5. ORGANISATIONAL CHALLENGES FOR INFORMAL SECTOR EMPLOYEES

Informal sector employees face numerous organisational challenges which make it difficult for them to effectively engage in collective bargaining. The informal sector plays an important role in supporting the economies of many countries including Zimbabwe. However, the sector is associated with bad working conditions for employees. In that regard, Nanfosso aptly captures this reality in the following words:⁷⁵

In most of developing countries, the informal sector is expanding rapidly, and is vast, heterogeneous in terms of activities and occupations. At times, one qualifies it as innovative, dynamic and a provider of opportunities for those with entrepreneurship skills. Yet, working conditions in this sector are too oppressive, and often unsafe; incomes of unregulated wage earners and the self-employed are usually at or below the poverty line; access to state-provided social protection, training, and

⁷² 'Who we are' (WIEGO, 2024) at <https://www.wiego.org/who-we-are> (last visited 27 December 2024).

⁷³ *ibid.*

⁷⁴ An example of such briefs was written by Rutendo Mudarikwa and Marlese von Broembsen with the title, "From 'Battles' to Collective Agreements Between Street Vendors and Local Authorities in Zimbabwe" and it analysed the work of ZCIEA in negotiating agreements with local authorities on issues affecting its membership including vending sites and their protection from harassment.

⁷⁵ Roger T. Nanfosso, 'Trade Union and the Informal Sector in Africa: Cameroon' (2016) 7 *Modern Economy* 1136.

social services are severely restricted; exploitation and infringement of workers' rights are common.

The aforementioned situation arises from various factors, some of which are addressed in this section. To begin with, a significant proportion of employees in the informal economy experience unstable livelihoods, with many living in conditions of extreme poverty. Their capacity to consistently pay membership dues is greatly limited and often subject to fluctuations or susceptible to external disruptions, such as economic downturns or natural disasters.⁷⁶ Failure to participate in trade union activities makes it difficult for trade unions to extend their operations to this category of employees. Further, informal traders are widely distributed, with the majority being quite small in scale. With home-based employees, organisers face challenges in identifying and coordinating them, particularly domestic workers employed in private residences, as they tend to be unseen and disconnected from one another.⁷⁷ Trade unions have pointed out there are challenges in maintaining membership and collecting dues under those circumstances, which constrains their potential for growth.⁷⁸

Closely related to the above is the fact that the interests, requirements, and ambitions of employees within the informal economy frequently diverge significantly from, or may even conflict with, those of current trade union members.⁷⁹ This happens when, for instance, vendors are competing for customers with formal businesses and the goods of the former are cheaper than the latter due to lower operational costs. This situation creates antagonism between the two set of employees to the extent that they may not join hands for the purposes of collective bargaining.

Du Toit adds a new dimension to the discussion by contending that employees find it difficult to negotiate collective bargaining agreements because employers in small enterprises are reluctant to join employers' organisations.⁸⁰ In Zimbabwe, employers' organisations are crucial as they are usually the representatives of employers of a particular industry when they negotiate industry level collective bargaining agreements.⁸¹ However, the participation of informal sector employees in Zimbabwe may not have any legal effect since they are bound by collective bargaining agreements that are negotiated for their industry.⁸² Further, Du Toit's argument does

⁷⁶ Labour and Economic Development Research Institute of Zimbabwe, *Strategies for Transitioning the Informal Economy to Formalisation in Zimbabwe* (Harare: Labour and Economic Development Research Institute of Zimbabwe and Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, 2015) 11.

⁷⁷ Chen, Bonner and Carré, n 48 above, 15.

⁷⁸ Schurman and Eaton, n 55 above, 21.

⁷⁹ *ibid.*

⁸⁰ Darcy Du Toit, 'The Small Business Sector: Deregulation or Collective Bargaining?' (1993) 14 *ILJ* 578.

⁸¹ See again, n 32 above, on the parties to employment councils.

⁸² See again, n 45 above, on the binding nature of collective bargaining agreements that are negotiated at industry level.

not apply to workplace level collective bargaining agreements as they are negotiated by a workers' committee and an individual employer.⁸³

Representation and internal democracy is another factor that weakens informal sector organisations and associations that represent employees. The absence of strong and democratic representation affects the allegiance of their members. In addition, an unrepresentative leadership may become increasingly out of touch with membership concerns.⁸⁴ Consequently, it becomes difficult to organise informal sector employees so that they can build a much stronger institution for collective bargaining with their employers.

Further, organisation demands significant time and substantial voluntary and unpaid effort. Informal employees often find it necessary to dedicate all their time to securing their livelihoods.⁸⁵ They do not find time to discuss issues that affect them. The consequence of this is a decline of trade unionism among informal employees, which subsequently impacts collective bargaining within that sector. Because of that, previous research suggests that negotiations between employers and employees are done at individual level and do not result in fruitful outcomes.⁸⁶

In the informal economy, formal contracts are virtually nonexistent. The majority of agreements are made verbally, which complicates the processes of monitoring and enforcement. In certain instances, an employee may be regarded as a 'member' of a household, with their labour serving as a means of supporting the family unit. Essentially, they assume the role of a contributing family employee.⁸⁷ Where it is difficult to determine who an employee is, one cannot talk of collective bargaining as this is done between employees and employers.

The mindset of influential stakeholders has also affected the recognition of the informal sector employees and are frequently victims of decisions by different tiers of the State.⁸⁸ In that regard, informal operators are often perceived as engaging in illegal activities due to their intentional evasion of taxation and regulatory frameworks. Additionally, informal activities are frequently regarded as inefficient and unproductive. However, numerous informal operators do contribute to various forms of taxation in Zimbabwe and would appreciate the advantages associated with legal recognition. Many local government policymakers and professionals in the built environment hold the belief that the removal of street vendors and informal settlements signifies progress, as the informal economy is viewed as detrimental to the concept of modernisation.⁸⁹ The failure to give legal recognition to some activities of the informal economy accompanied by the right policies also means that employees

⁸³ See again, n 27 above, on the parties who negotiate collective bargaining agreements at workplace level.

⁸⁴ Chen, Bonner and Carré, n 48 above, 25.

⁸⁵ Labour and Economic Development Research Institute of Zimbabwe, n 76 above, 11.

⁸⁶ Muchichwa, n 69 above, 139.

⁸⁷ *ibid.*

⁸⁸ Chen, Bonner and Carré, n 48 above, 27.

⁸⁹ *ibid.*

who work in unrecognised activities may not fully enjoy all the rights and privileges accorded by the law, including the right to collective bargaining.

Finally, another challenge that should not be ignored is that many employees lack awareness of their labour rights and obligations. This is because there is no adequate education on these rights which include the right to collective bargaining. To that end, they are subjected to the conditions that are offered by their employers.⁹⁰ Even where employees are aware of their rights, they are afraid to lose their jobs.⁹¹ It is submitted that such fear emanate from the absence of coordinated efforts to improve their conditions of employment through a system of collective bargaining that goes beyond an individual employer or employee.

6. THE WAY FORWARD

The aforementioned challenges that affect collective bargaining in the informal sector needs fixing through a holistic approach. In that regard, no single prescription can cure all the identified ills. Therefore, this part discusses various ways of strengthening collective bargaining in the Zimbabwe's informal sector. In the process, the proposed solutions have a direct link with the identified challenges that prevent the informal sector employees from fully enjoying the right to collective bargaining with the attendant improvement in their conditions of work.

To start with, the government should accelerate efforts to formalise the informal sector. Formalisation ensures informal sector employees' freedom from discrimination, access to occupational health and safety standards, the opportunity to participate in and benefit from social protection systems (including health and pension schemes), and the right to organise and engage in collective bargaining.⁹² Further, establishing formal recognition for this segment of the economy, among other benefits, generates sustainable employment opportunities and tackles issues such as unemployment, underemployment, poverty, gender disparity, insufficient representation, and precarious employment conditions.⁹³ It has been observed that the inclination of numerous individuals to transition from the informal sector to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is continually influenced by the ongoing evaluation

⁹⁰ For instance, in interviews carried out by Muchichwa, n 69 above, 139, one of the respondents replied as follows: "There is no dialogue, the employer gives you what he wants. With the desire to earn a livelihood one just stays in employment"

⁹¹ Du Toit, n 80 above, 578.

⁹² Labour and Economic Development Research Institute of Zimbabwe, n 76 above, 2. Various organisations, including the Zimbabwe Congress of Trade Unions (ZCTU) and the Zimbabwe Chamber of Informal Economy Associations (ZCIEA) have been urging the government to strive for the achievement of the goals outlined in the Transition from the Informal to the Formal Economy Recommendation (R204) which requires member states to support the movement of employees and economic entities from the informal sector to the formal economy, while upholding the fundamental rights of employees and guaranteeing access to income security, sustainable livelihoods, and entrepreneurial opportunities.

⁹³ Tavonga J. Zvobgo, 'Collective bargaining and collective agreements in Africa' (2019) Turin School of Development Working Paper No. 11 *International Training Centre of the ILO* 27.

of the costs associated with informality versus the benefits of formalisation.⁹⁴ As long as the costs remain less than the potential gains, they are likely to continue operating within the informal sector. In that regard, the government should provide incentives that attract the informal sector so that it can see the need to formalise its businesses.

One of the ways of incentivising the informal sector is for the government to collaborate with development partners and financial institutions in order to promote viable projects aimed at alleviating poverty by facilitating access to financing for informal sector businesses and offering microfinance credit. Additionally, it should invest in essential infrastructure and technology while providing informal sector businesses with crucial information regarding domestic, regional, and international markets.⁹⁵ This ensures the graduation of the informal sector from small and unrecognisable entities into formidable business ventures that can easily participate in the formal economy. Once the informal sector grows into strong entities, it becomes easier for it to comply with labour laws and for the sector to pay improved wages. Formalisation increases the base of formal employees which can be organised easily by trade unions. The growth of trade union membership also means that trade unions themselves have a larger base to collect membership dues from. Strong trade unions stand a better chance to negotiate better working conditions with employers.

Another way of ensuring that there is strong collective bargaining in the informal sector is for the government to take advantage of the Labour Act which provides for statutory bargaining councils. The Minister may, when the national interest necessitates, request any registered employers' organisation or federation of such organisations and any registered trade union or federation of such trade unions to establish an employment council and to seek its registration in accordance with the provisions of the Labour Act.⁹⁶ In the event that those who have been requested to apply for the registration of an employment council by the Minister fail to do so, the Minister can appoint any members of employers and employees to constitute the employment council.⁹⁷ It is submitted that it is in the national interest that the informal sector must have a strong system of collective bargaining because it employs the largest component of employees in Zimbabwe.

In addition, the government is bound by the Constitution of Zimbabwe to ensure that its declaration of rights is fully promoted and protected.⁹⁸ One of such fundamental rights is the right of every person, which includes the informal sector employees, to fair labour standards and practices including the right to be paid a fair

⁹⁴ Nanfosso, (n 75 above), 1151.

⁹⁵ Tavonga Njaya, 'Informal Sector, Panacea to the High Unemployment in Zimbabwe? Case of Informal Sector Enterprises of Harare Metropolitan' (2015) 2 *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies* 105.

⁹⁶ Section 57 of the Labour Act.

⁹⁷ *ibid.*

⁹⁸ Section 44 of the Constitution of Zimbabwe.

and reasonable wage.⁹⁹ To that end, the government should ensure that there are enough and effective employment councils that cover all the categories of employees in that sector in order to fulfil the spirit of the constitution. Such employment councils can be formed by existing or newly registered trade unions with a special focus on the informal sector.

Labour inspections can assist in enhancing employees' protection in the informal sector. In that regard, labour officers¹⁰⁰ are empowered to enter into any premises without notice for the purposes of gathering information about the conditions of employment for employees who are employed therein.¹⁰¹ Labour officers have the potential to be instrumental in upholding the minimum work standards mandated by law for the informal sector, ensuring that the rights of employees, including their right to engage in collective bargaining, are honoured within the workplace. Given that industry-level collective bargaining agreements are binding on the entire industry to which they pertain, labour officers can play a significant role in ensuring that employers within the informal sector adhere to the stipulations outlined in the pertinent collective bargaining agreements.¹⁰² However, they need sufficient resources in order to carry out their duties. It is the duty of the government to ensure that its state officials, that is, labour officers are equipped with sufficient resources to perform their designated responsibilities efficiently.

The absence of outreach and awareness initiatives has been identified as a significant challenge in the informal sector.¹⁰³ Consequently, it is advisable for trade unions or informal sector associations to establish programmes specifically for employees in the informal sector, with the objective of educating them about their rights, fostering decent work conditions, and facilitating the organisation and recruitment of these employees.¹⁰⁴ To implement this, trade unions or associations should prioritise the allocation of budgets for these activities. Furthermore, within the framework of outreach programmes, trade unions or associations ought to broaden their services to include education and training for informal sector employees, thereby enhancing skills development for the economy, as well as promoting literacy, health and safety initiatives. Although the ZCIEA has participated in training programmes for informal sector employees, its programmes have not specifically targeted wage earners in the informal sector but it has treated all members of that sector as

⁹⁹ *ibid*, section 65(1).

¹⁰⁰ These are State employees who are appointed in terms of section 21 of the Labour Act to carry out functions that are assigned to them by the law.

¹⁰¹ Section 126 of the Labour Act.

¹⁰² See again, n 45 above, on the binding nature of collective bargaining agreements that are negotiated at industry level.

¹⁰³ Muchichwa, n 69 above, 152.

¹⁰⁴ *ibid*.

employees with similar challenges.¹⁰⁵ Further, the outreach programmes are insufficient and infrequently conducted, especially considering the substantial growth of the informal sector, which has expanded significantly as a result of high unemployment rates and economic difficulties.¹⁰⁶

Given that employees in the informal sector find it difficult to sustain their associations through monetary contributions, trade unions or associations representing them have limited funding to finance training programmes. It means they have to seek funding from other organisations including those that finance human rights programmes like non-governmental organisations (NGOs). These organisations are in a position to secure funding from third parties who have the capacity to bankroll training and education for employees in the informal sector. As alluded to earlier on, such programmes should not treat employees as homogenous but they should correctly profile them and deal with each group's needs.

Further, formal and informal employees should unite on their own. This unity could be achieved through collaborations between all organisations representing employees which includes trade unions and associations. It has been rightly observed that in the contemporary global economy, the workforce associated with a specific industry, regardless of their employment with a single company, comprises not only the primary formal employees but also encompasses all individuals involved in the supply chain such as those working in the informal sector.¹⁰⁷ In that regard, the formal and informal sector complements each other and employees should act in unison in order to strengthen their collective will and ability to effectively engage in collective bargaining with employers.

It has also been argued that it might be helpful if trade unions form area-based employee representative bodies rather than workplace-based ones.¹⁰⁸ Under that model, elected officials representing the collective membership of various trade unions or associations within a given area could function as the primary union framework for addressing local workplace issues. It is submitted that this is another way of uniting trade unions and organising the informal sector in Zimbabwe. This is because it is widely spread and various activities are mixed within the same area. It becomes economical to have representatives based on area as opposed to a particular trade or industry. However, the existence of different industries should be recognised and maintained as they involve different working conditions. The role of such area

¹⁰⁵ For instance, it has dealt with court cases, negotiated with local authorities for its members to get vending sites, challenged national and local policies on behalf of its members and hosted national symposiums on behalf of its members. However, none of these activities clearly separated employers and employees in the informal sector. For a detailed discussion of the activities of ZCIEA, see Gwisai and Matika, n 5 above, 11-17.

¹⁰⁶ For instance, according to see Gwisai and Matika, n 5 above at 13, the ZCIEA has only managed to successfully train 12 Paralegal Officers and with 15 more currently undergoing training. These numbers are too low to cover the entire informal sector in Zimbabwe.

¹⁰⁷ Chen, Bonner and Carré, n 48 above, 37.

¹⁰⁸ Du Toit, n 80 above, 580.

representatives should be to defend employees' rights as provided for by labour legislation and the relevant collective bargaining agreements for that industry or workplace.

7. CONCLUSION

This article has examined the rights of employees in the informal sector regarding collective bargaining and proposed methods to improve its efficacy in Zimbabwe. It has been emphasised that the right to collective bargaining is enshrined in the declaration of rights within the Constitution of Zimbabwe. Consequently, both the State and private entities, including employers, are required to adhere to its stipulations. Additionally, it has been noted that the Labour Act, which serves as the primary legislation governing labour relations in the informal sector, recognises the right to collective bargaining, thereby operationalising the constitutional guarantees. The Labour Act acknowledges both statutory and non-statutory forms of collective bargaining. However, it is the statutory collective bargaining that receives protection under the Act, which mandates the obligation to engage in good faith negotiations. Furthermore, the Labour Act accommodates collective bargaining at both the industry and workplace levels, granting trade unions a degree of authority over the process. In this context, the law underscores the importance of employee organisation in maintaining a strong voice within employment relations.

The primary issue is that the current academic discourse regarding informal sector employees in Zimbabwe often categorises them as a homogeneous group, overlooking the diverse employment relationships that exist within this sector. While some individuals are self-employed, there are also wage earners who work for informal sector employers. Further, the activities within the informal sector are linked to various formal sector industries. Consequently, those classified as 'employees' under the Labour Act are entitled to the full range of labour rights outlined in both the Constitution of Zimbabwe and the Labour Act, which includes the right to engage in collective bargaining. An effective collective bargaining system is essential for enhancing the working conditions of employees in the informal sector.

It has been demonstrated that employees in the informal sector encounter various organisational challenges that must be addressed for them to fully exercise their right to collective bargaining. Among these challenges are insufficient resources for organising informal employees, the lack of formal employment contracts, difficulties in clarifying the nature of employment relationships, the absence of internal democracy within the associations that represent informal sector employees, and a general lack of awareness regarding their rights, to mention a few. Addressing these issues necessitates a comprehensive approach, as previously discussed, when proposing solutions. It is essential that there be collaborative efforts among the government, employers, trade unions, civic organisations, and associations

representing informal sector employees to ensure the protection of the fundamental rights of these employees, including their right to engage in collective bargaining. The provision of resources, along with a commitment to adequately support vulnerable employees in the informal sector, serves as a solution to many of the issues that have led to these individuals enduring poor working conditions. This initiative must be reinforced by appropriate policies that bolster the overall economic landscape and tackle the economic challenges contributing to the growth of the informal economy in Zimbabwe.